

OBJECTS OF THE STATE ADMINISTRATION SYSTEM AND THEIR SOCIAL CHARACTERS

Tashkoziyeva Madinabonu

Student of Fergana State University

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Abstract: The state management system is nothing but human activity and character, striving to organize and rationally manage his efforts to achieve his life goal. Management system is a type of socio-political activity related to one or another level, directly or indirectly, with a person, his self-management, management. Therefore, the paradigmatic features and fundamental tasks of the state administration system are a reflection of the human life goal, the desire for self-management.

Key words: Social determination, non-reproducibility, Social life, democratic society, immanent feature

Man is both subject and object for any management system. In scientific literature, the subject is divided into active, managerial, object - inactive, executive. An active attitude to social life is considered a subject, and observation of social processes or absolute indifference to them is considered a characteristic of an object. "The concept of an object," it is said, "in the work "Philosophy of Knowledge", - represents a thing, an event, an event, etc., opposite to the subject, to which the practical, evaluative and cognitive activity of the subject is directed... The moment of relativity in the concepts of "subject" and "object" exists: if the same thing is an object at one time, it can be a subject at another time, and vice versa... A. is the subject of being a student and the same V. for the student it can be an object of knowledge. As L. Feuerbach said: "I am a subject for myself and an object for others, so the conclusion is that "I" can be both a subject and an object!" So, this is an axiom that a person can be a subject or an object at the same time. However, the question arises. If a person is both a subject and an object of knowledge and control, what will be their functional characteristics? Any management requires that the functions, tasks, and spheres of actions of the subject and the object be clearly defined, right?! This calls into question whether a person can be both a subject and an object for himself at the same time. We will dwell on this epistemological problem in detail in the next topic, now we must say that whether a person is a subject or an object of management depends first of all on his will, knowledge and activities aimed at implementing it in life. Because it is impossible to separate and analyze the thoughts about the subject and the object from this approach. No matter how much social determination affects the human consciousness and self-expression, a person acts as a subject (active) or an object (passive observer) only after passing through the synthesis of his spiritual and spiritual consciousness, thinking and life experience. It is this "internal synthesis" that determines the social characteristics of the subject or object and serves their manifestation in the socio-political existence.

It is known that human activity, the life goal of a person, his desire for self-management (self-manifestation through this management, use of his inner spiritual-

spiritual, intellectual potential) is a dynamic phenomenon. This dynamic feature makes the control system also a dynamic action, a dynamic system. If the management system loses its dynamic character, cannot respond to human aspirations, it becomes a conservative reality and has a negative impact on the dynamic development of society.

At the same time, the social deterministic influence is too much, sometimes beyond the capabilities of the management system. In this case, the management system cannot respond to social determinism, as a result, the management system loses its viability, flexibility and responsiveness.

It is true that social determinism leads lower management systems to operate with high responsibility, high organization, to work in accordance with the dynamic development of society, but it is obliged to take into account the self-management capabilities of the management system. For example, in the departments of religious, educational and spiritual affairs and working with women under the citizens' assembly established in our republic, it is observed that public women approach their duties with extreme formality. That's why almost 80% of active women in this department work for one year, 10-12% - for two years, and 6-7% for three years. One of the main reasons for this is that the higher authorities constantly demand various reports, they demand to hold events that do not correspond to the financial capabilities of the department and the citizens' assembly. Therefore, there must be a balance and harmony between the state administration system and women's socio-political activity, the possibilities of implementing this activity.

According to the subject of our research, the object of the public administration system on a wide, socio-political scale is the women's layer, the women's audience. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, this layer and audience make up 51% of the population of our country. But this layer, the audience, has its own internal systems and social characteristics. Women need to be taken into account when it comes to making them subjects of socio-political existence.

By the internal systems of the women's layer and audience, we mean their psychophysiological state, ontogenetic growth, development. They:

- little girl, little girl;
- childhood and adolescence;
- adulthood;
- motherhood (reproductive);
- non-reproductiveness;

- can be divided into periods such as old age. During these periods, certain psychophysiological changes and shifts occur in the female body and condition, which cannot but affect a woman's attitude to social life. It is known from special observations that women's socio-political activity mainly coincides with the non-reproductive period. This period can be defined as 40-60 years old.

During the non-reproductive period, women are freed from childbirth and child-rearing, they have time to participate in social life after family chores. In addition, by this period, women will have a certain knowledge and practical experience about social life, management technology. The non-reproductive period is the reproductive period of women's socio-political existence. This factor should be taken into account when involving women in socio-political activities.

Experience shows that not all women can be socio-political activists, making such a demand on them is ignorance of human psychology and the laws of social existence. In many cases, women prefer not to be active in social and political life, but to express themselves in the spheres of spiritual education, culture, folk art and recreation. Doctor of philosophy V. Alimasov followed Western philosophers: "A woman lacks sociability, self-awareness and courage, she can show these qualities towards her family. "She does not struggle to express herself as a person like a man, the feeling of getting used to life and relationships in a woman's nature is superior," he writes. Here, the scientist refers to the above factor, that is, not all women are active in the social and political sphere. Even such a situation is not observed in all men. However, it is difficult to agree with the words of V. Alimasov that "a woman does not fight to express herself as a person like a man, she lacks courage and sociability." Isn't giving birth to a child, putting him on his feet, forming him as a human being, carrying out household chores diligently, every day, without melting, with patience, a unique form of courage and socialization?

V. Alimasov said, "Social and political activity of men remains an axiom. Ignoring this factor destroys the idea of any gender equality," Doctor of Philosophy A. Huseynova rightfully objected to his opinion, and wrote: "Firstly, the majority of men in state management activities, while their socio-political activity is still an axiom, there is no reason to describe it as Yes, it cannot be denied that men predominate in the upper echelons of management, but socio-political existence is not defined solely by this echelon. Without the socio-political activity of the middle and lower ranks, the upper ranks cannot achieve any success. Women make up 70-85 percent of the middle and lower ranks of socio-legal, cultural-educational, educational, communication, medical and service sectors. So, can the socio-political activism of men be an axiom? Of course not. Second, can men in senior leadership negatively impact gender equality? No. The upper echelons can adopt laws, directives, programs and plans that suit their interests, but if they are not in line with the interests of society and democratic values, it is difficult to bring about social results. Therefore, ensuring gender equality is a reality related to the demands of democratic development of the society, which cannot be imagined to be ensured only through the upper level.

In fact, the debate here is about how much a woman is a subject and how much an object in socio-political existence. While V. Alimasov is inclined to the opinion that some women are socio-politically active (subject), and most of them are socio-politically inactive (object), A. Huseynova starts from the activity of women in other fields, thus she wants to expand the range of socio-political activity. It is true that other spheres do not remain unaffected by socio-political life, but although they are not highly active in socio-political existence, the current democratic society, adopted legal and regulatory documents, state policy, women, according to their wishes and legitimate aspirations, , ready to turn into active subjects of socio-political existence. Now it's about women moving themselves, turning themselves from object to subject.

For the system of public administration, not only active women, the subject, but also the audience, the executive, the objects that apply the adopted laws and decisions to their actions are necessary. Being the object of a management system does not absolve either the management system or the object from responsibility to the other. To fulfill this responsibility, the object is necessary for the subject, and the subject is necessary for the

object. This is not only a condition for establishing management, but also for ensuring the development of society through the rational organization of social relations.

Socio-political activity is an immanent feature of the object (woman). Aristotle was right when he said that man is a social and political being. A person knows that his actions are not only related to the interests and aspirations of others, but he also knows that he is a factor in harmonizing his actions with the activities and aspirations of others, forming groups, teams, and parties. Because "needs and necessity of participation in socio-political relations create a basis for every citizen to realize that interests can be expressed and satisfied only in group form. The processes of understanding that different interests of different social groups and classes enter into conflicts and conflicts, and that they cannot be resolved without reconciliation and balancing, naturally form the needs for a populist society and political power.

Socio-political activity does not become internal immanent features of the object, it requires objectification in socio-political existence. Activity that is not objectified remains a fantasy, a dream, just a wish, a plan. Therefore, the state administration system, which follows democratic principles, puts the objectification of socio-political activity on the agenda and considers it as the source of its development. It is the duty of every democratic state to call for objectification.

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